

The principle of “the constancy of the speed of light”

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Abstract

After it was confirmed by many measurements that the speed of light was constant, whatever the speed of the source or the receiver, Einstein stated the principle of “the constancy of the speed of light”, in any inertial reference frame, to developped its SR relativity theory.

In this paper we will show how the principle of "the constancy of the speed of light", in any inertial reference frame, can be demonstrated in a natural way. It will allow us to explain readily the results of Michelson Morley and Sagnac experiments.

Also, another relativity theory is presented briefly.

This two facts renders unnecessary Einstein SR theory.

1 Introduction

The first significant measure of the speed of light was done by James Bradley in 1729, and he got the value of 301 000 km/s. After that, Hippolyte Fizeau and Leon Foucault obtained respectively 315 000 km/s (1849) and 298 000 km/s (1862). In the following years the values obtained by Alfred Cornu (1870), Albert Michelson (1878), Simon Newcomb (1882), Henri Perrotin (1898, 1902), were more and more converging towards the value we know nowadays ([1]).

At about the same period, in 1873, JC Maxwell established his theory for the propagation of electromagnetic waves in the form of eight equations. Some years later, in 1884, it was Heaviside who simplified this theory to the four equations that are known nowadays. From this theory and from the measured values of the permittivity and the permeability characteristics of the vacuum, it is possible to calculate the velocity of electromagnetic waves. From the first estimates, JC Maxwell, finding that the value was close to the measured value of the speed of light known at that time, concluded that light was an electromagnetic wave, whose propagation was governed by his equations.

Since the speed of light is obtained by the electromagnetic properties of the propagating medium, it is not a physical constant. It is more or less like the speed of sound. Nevertheless, it is a fact that in our neighbourhood the light speed is a constant and independent of the speed of the source and/or the observer (Arago's experiments).

Then, JC Maxwell promoted the ancient idea of an "ether" for the propagation of light and he supposed it was stationary. The problem he faced with other scientists was how light is propagating in this medium when the light source is in motion with respect to this stationary ether. This was the great question at the end of the 19th century.

Unfortunately for Maxwell and the advocates of ether for the propagation of light, Michelson and others, their thought about the emission of light led them to misinterpret the quasi null result of Michelson and Morley experiments.

They had in mind the effect of air wind when a vehicle is moving with respect to stationary air. If you throw something out of the vehicle, it will be slowed down in the direction of the throw and its trajectory curved in the perpendicular direction. They supposed that light was emitted from matter, and then if matter was moving with respect to the stationary ether, there will be an “ether wind” effect that will modify the motion of light, and can be measured.

Michelson and Morley experiments showed that there was no “ether wind” and then the idea of an ether for the propagation of light was abandoned and scientists have searched for a solution to explain the null result.

At almost the same moment, faced with the impossibility to transform Maxwell’s electromagnetic wave equation from an inertial reference frame to another one in motion with Newton transformation rules, Einstein derived its SR theory, stating the principle of the constancy of the speed of light in any inertial reference frame, whatever the speed of the source or the observer.

Using its new theory, Einstein was able to explain the null result, to the great despair of Michelson:”I gave birth to a monster”.

When in physics we are obliged to state a principle, this means that we don’t understand the real phenomenon underlying. It’s an admission of weakness.

2 The constancy of the speed of light

2.1 Einstein’s principle

Let’s start looking at the statement of this principle stated by Silberstein, one of the former follower of Einstein SR theory. He stated in 1922 the principle of the constancy of light by ([2]): “*Light is propagated in vacuo, relatively to any inertial reference system, with a velocity c , constant and equal for all directions, no matter whether the source emitting it is fixed or moving with respect to that system*”.

In this reference, G. Boulder, compared this statement to the one given by JC Maxwell: “*the Maxwell-Lorentz theory supposed that light is propagated in a universal stationary medium (ether) with a velocity c , characteristic of the medium and independent of the motion of its source*”.

And G. Boulder concluded that this statement is completely different of the one of Einstein, since the statement of JC Maxwell implies that “*the propagation of the light, relative to any inertial system in motion relative to the ether, would be non-uniform and anisotropic, i.e. it would be propagated relative to the inertial system with different speeds in different directions*”.

This conclusion of G. Boulder is incorrect and we will see why. In the following of this paper, we will take Maxwell universal stationary medium as a reference for the propagation of light. Also we will suppose that this medium has electromagnetic properties given by the permittivity and the permeability, measured in what we call the vacuum. We will then make a hypothesis about the emission and absorption of light by matter and see, with this hypothesis, how it is possible to demonstrate the reality of the constancy of the speed of light.

2.2 Emission of light and the constancy of the speed of light

Emission of light is done by a transfer of energy from matter to the outside of matter which is called by the scientific community “vacuum” . Whether the emission is done in a spontaneous way or is stimulated, matter emit light with a characteristic energy which can be calculated precisely with current models of quantum mechanics.

It is considered also that the light emitted from matter, when it leave the matter source, is in the form of a particle and an associated wave. It is called a photon.

The problematic of the emission of light can be stated as this: from where the photon comes? of what is it issued? and where it goes when it is absorbed? It can be showed that the energy of the photon comes

from matter at the emission and goes back to matter at absorption. But it is impossible that the photon comes directly from matter since, for example in a light bulb, the number of photons emitted is about 10^{19} photons/s, and the light bulb will survive long enough ([3])!

The simplest way to consider the emission of a photon from matter is to conjecture that the photon doesn't come from it, but is created in situ in the propagating medium itself, that we will call ether. We suppose also that, whatever the frequency of the photon, it is emitted instantaneously inside the ether medium. This instantaneity is reasonable since the wave length of the wave of a photon emitted by a hydrogen atom is of the order of 10^{-7} m, while the size of an electron is much less than 10^{-18} m, if even it has a size!

We assume that a photon is not emitted from matter but is created instantaneously inside the stationary ether. It may be, for example, an interaction between an electron and the ether which can be responsible of this creation. From many experiments, it is well known that a photon is emitted (created), in particular, when an electron is accelerated/decelerated from its state of motion. The acceleration/deceleration of the electron, which is imbedded in the ether, could be the initiation of this creation, the energy lost by the electron in this interaction given instantaneously to the photon. There are other mechanisms creating a photon.

In our assumption, after the creation of the photon, the matter object is pursuing its motion relative to the ether without giving any velocity to the created photon. The created photon, whatever the frequency of its associated wave, propagates in the ether at a constant speed due to the electromagnetic properties of the medium. Also, it goes in a straight line, starting from the point source of creation in a definite direction.

Let's look at a thought experiment to illustrate the behavior of the photon when and after it is created. Imagine somebody is on a train and throw a ball from the window when the train is moving, in the perpendicular direction of the velocity of the train. Then, if the train is moving in vacuum, the ball will get the speed of the train, added to the impulse of the throw. This way of thinking for the emission of light was the one of the scientists who have tried to explain Michelson null results.

Now suppose that the ball is attached to a pole standing along the track and that a mechanism will give the same impulse to the ball, in the same direction as previously, when the train passes by the ball. In the case of the vacuum, the ball will go in a straight line with the initial impulse, and no impulse from the train. In this case the mechanism giving the impulse represent the kinetic energy given to the photon by the interaction of an electron with ether.

With these hypothesis on emission of light, the photon will always go at the speed it gets from the medium and with no ether wind effect. It stays in the direction of the emission indefinitely until it encounters matter.

Also, if we suppose that a photon is absorbed instantly, meaning that whatever its frequency the transfer of energy is instantaneous, then it is understandable that the light speed is also independent of the speed of the observer.

It is straightforward that the light speed is the same in any inertial reference frame, whatever its velocity, since light and matter are not linked in any way. It seems like matter and light are evolving in parallel, interacting instantaneously at emission and at absorption.

With the conditions above, whatever the speed of an inertial reference frame from which the light is emitted (an atom), the speed of light is only dependant on the electromagnetic properties of the static ether in which it is created and then propagated at a constant speed.

It should be noted that during the propagation of the photon and its associated wave, there is no electric charge in the surroundings. It is only the permittivity and the permeability of the medium which gives the propagation of light.

So far, we got focused on the propagation in the propagating medium. Another interrogation appears for light going through transparent matter. Although this issue is out of the subject of Einstein principle, it can be conjectured that the medium ether embedded in matter atoms. The result is a modification of the electromagnetic properties which results in a slower speed of light.

2.3 Michelson and Morley experiment

It can be seen easily that with these hypothesis on the creation of light inside the propagating medium, outside the matter, there is no possibility of an ether wind. Using the hypothesis above about the creation of light, Jean David obtained the null result ([4]). Michelson didn't see any "ether wind", not because ether don't exist, but because there can't be a wind at all.

2.4 Sagnac experiment

Georges Sagnac resumed the experience of Michelson and Morley by fixing the interferometer to a rotating plate such that both beams of light did a complete tour, but in opposite directions. The plate was rotated and interference fringes measured between the two beams.

We can show that the fringes phenomenon is due to the different distances that light travels for each ray of light due to the rotation of the plate, creating a Doppler effect. The duration of the journey, taking into account the velocity of the plate and the direction of each beam, is given by:

$$\Delta t_1 = \frac{2\pi R}{c - \varpi R} \quad (1)$$

$$\Delta t_2 = \frac{2\pi R}{c + \varpi R} \quad (2)$$

with R the radius of the circular ring, c the speed of light, ϖ the plate's rotation speed.

By subtracting the two route times, we obtain an equal shift of interference fringes equal to $4S\varpi/\lambda c$, with S the internal surface of the route of the beams and λ the light wavelength. It is simply the addition of speeds in Newtonian physics, which is valid either if the ether exists or either at low speed if Einstein SR theory of relativity is valid.

But, when the velocity of the rotating apparatus is increased close to the light speed, there is no relativity effect since the apparatus is staying in the same inertial reference frame. Then the equations above are still valid.

2.5 One-way measurement of the speed of light

In litterature one can see this type of measurement which are presented to argue with the constancy of the speed of light in any inertial reference frame. It shows that the velocity of the earth must be added or substracted, depending in the direction of the earth motion relative to each light beam.

These results are in perfect agreement with the constancy of the speed of light. Like in Sagnac experiment, we must take into account the fact that the receiver is moving with the earth giving an addition effect of the speed of the earth.

3 Relativity

It is strange that science community is ignoring the existence of another relativity theory, proposed by Young-Sea Huang in the years of 1980 ([5]). This theory is able to show that all the laws of physics hold good whatever the velocity of the reference frame. The big difference between this new one and the one of Einstein is that the transformation used by Young-Sea Huang is in the velocity space.

The velocity reference Young-Sea Huang uses is the light velocity. But, as he mention, he could use any other velocity in reference, like the velocity of sound for example. It will make no difference, only to compare the evolution of events with speeds too much higher is not much practicable. The only aspect to respect is to use a constant reference velocity, which is the case for light.

By the way, if you consider the energy conservation law, since we cannot express this law in space-time coordinates, Einstein SR is unable to show that this law holds good in any inertial reference frame!

This conservation of energy, which holds good in any inertial reference frame, is also a way to show that anybody in a vehicle speeding close to light velocity, will be getting old as a person staying on earth, given that all biology equations can be rid of the time parameter.

With the above relativity theory, there is no fancy things about time. In it, time duration is the same as Newton and every events occurring in the universe are simultaneous.

4 Conclusion

The constancy of the speed of light in any inertial reference frame is a reality. With our hypothesis on the creation of a photon in-situ and instantaneously in the ether, it is obvious that the speed of light is the same whatever the motion of the inertial frame of reference with respect to the ether. This constancy of the speed of light is true as long as the electromagnetic properties of the medium stay constants.

Moreover, since the velocity of a wave propagating in the ether depends on the ether electromagnetic properties, a matter wave cannot get a velocity superior to the speed of light.

This demonstration renders useless Einstein SR theory. Another relativity theory seems to be more useful and not doing fancy things on the time parameter ([6]).

References

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